

1 **Cellular evolution involving OGFOD catalytic function.**

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7 Mutation is the driving force of evolution. Evolution can be studied at the population level at the scale of
8 years or generations, and at the cellular level at the scale of cell divisions (passages in *in vitro* systems).
9 The prevailing theory of the mechanism by which mutation and cellular evolution proceeds in cells with
10 mutant isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) family enzyme is production of a metabolite that is essentially
11 genotoxic as a result of catalytic poisoning of the ketoglutarate domain of epigenetic enzymes from the
12 JMJD histone lysine methyltransferase family and resulting mutagenesis. We present evidence here
13 indicating the likely function of molecules from the OGFOD (OGFOD1/2/3) family of enzymes in a related
14 process, in sum representing the collection of processes by which cellular evolution resulting from
15 metabolic devolvement can proceed.

16 Citations

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